

Perspective-based specification of machine learning-enabled systems

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* Required

Approach

Our work considers two artifacts that with your help we want to improve. The figures below show the following artifacts.

- (i) the ML perspective-based task and concern diagram
- (ii) the ML requirements specification template
- (iii) the perspective-based specification for Project A
- (iv) the perspective-based specification for Project B

Perspective-based task and concern diagram

ML requirements specification template

ML objectives	User Experience Perspective				Infrastructure Perspective
	Accountability	Cost	Forceness		Data streaming
Problem & context				Visualization	Execution engine
Organizational goals	Frequency	Interactiveness	Value		
User goals	Data Perspective				Incremental Learning
	Baseline	Data operations	Distribution	Quantity	Source
Model goals	Timeliness	Inherent data quality			Integration
ML functionality	Model Perspective				Storage
	Algorithm	Explainability	Inference time	Input & Output	Learning time
Leading indicators	Maintainability	ML problem type	Model performance	Model size	Reproducibility
Customer expectations	Exploitability				Telemetry

ML perspective-based specification for Project A

ML objectives	User Experience Perspective				Infrastructure Perspective
	Accountability	Cost	Forceness		Data streaming
Problem & context	Strong odors emitted by industrial units that make communities uncomfortable.	The operator is completely responsible for decisions taken in order to reduce community protests.	The operator shall be aware of the sanctions in case of not preventing community protests.	Taking decisions based on the predictions is not mandatory.	Data streaming The data shall be streamed by the real time data management system (Microsoft Stream Analytics tool).
Organizational goals	Frequency Avoid being sanctioned by the environmental authority for emitting strong odors.	Interactiveness The operator shall receive a prediction every 5 minutes.	Value The operator shall have transparency on the reduction of complaints.	Visualization The predictions of the model shall be presented in a dashboard in an interactive way according to the approved prototype.	Execution engine The model shall be deployed in a cloud computing service (Microsoft Azure).
User goals	Baseline Data emission alerts shall be accurate to allow decisions to be made to reduce community complaints.	Data operations The data shall meet the constraints (e.g., min max values, data types), defined in the baseline dataset.	Distribution The dataset shall be split in some degree into training and test data.	Quantity The training and test dataset shall have data points as needed to build a valuable model.	Source The data shall be searched in a database supported by the third party data providing service.
Model goals	Timeliness Accuracy, precision, recall shall be higher than 70%.	Timeliness The data shall be available for use in real time.	Inherent data quality The data shall be real usage data and meet concerns related to ethics, accuracy, bias, completeness, consistency and credibility as much as possible.		Integration The dashboard shall consume the model as a web service (Microsoft Azure endpoints).
ML functionality	Algorithm Logistic regression.	Explainability The model shall provide information on the most importance features to explain its decisions.	Inference time The model shall infer its results in less than a minute.	Input & Output The training and test dataset shall have images as needed to build a valuable model.	Learning time The creation/training of the model shall be automated by using a pipeline.
Leading indicators	Maintainability Daily dashboard usage percentage and reduce the number of complaints from the community in 30%.	ML problem type Predict categories (classification problem).	Model performance The model shall meet accuracy, precision and recall higher than 70%.	Model size The model size shall not break the inference time and the model explainability.	Storage The ML artifacts (e.g., model, datasets, segments) shall be stored in a cloud service on Microsoft Azure.
Customer expectations	Exploitability The system shall accurately avoid emitting strong odors, allowing to prevent community complaints.	Exploitability The model creation shall follow best coding practices (e.g., coding conventions PEP-8, SOLID design principles) and be documented according to Decoding PEP-257.			Telemetry The system shall collect and allow monitoring user interaction data and model performance.

ML perspective-based specification for Project B

ML objectives	User Experience Perspective				Infrastructure Perspective
	Accountability	Cost	Forceness		Data streaming
Problem & context	The disproportionate burning of gases causing high money costs.	The operator is completely responsible for decisions taken in order to reduce the burning gases.	The operator shall be aware of the sanctions in case of not preventing bad burning gases.	Other systems shall use the predictions to take automatic actions in the refineries.	Data streaming The videos shall be streamed by accessing the IP address of the camera that points at the flare.
Organizational goals	Frequency Increase the refinery's profitability through an efficient safe flare gas burning.	Interactiveness The operator shall receive a notification of the flare every minute.	Value The operator shall have transparency on the reduction of bad burning gases.	Visualization The predictions of the model shall be presented in a dashboard in an interactive way according to the approved prototype.	Execution engine The model shall be deployed to several customer servers and consumed locally.
User goals	Baseline The gas burning classifications shall be accurate allowing the operator to activate the automatic work mode.	Data operations The images shall be extracted from videos, cropped and labeled as needed.	Distribution The images shall be split in some rationale degree into training and test data.	Quantity The training and test dataset shall have images as needed to build a valuable model.	Source The images shall be obtained from videos that are sent by the customer due to permission issues.
Model goals	Timeliness Accuracy, precision, recall = 70%.	Timeliness The videos from a month ago shall be available for use.	Inherent data quality The images shall meet bias, completeness, consistency, credibility and real usage.		Integration The model shall be integrated with an inference engine so that it can define operation operation rules.
ML functionality	Algorithm Neural Networks	Explainability Does not apply.	Inference time The model shall infer a set of images (40) in less than a minute.	Input & Output Input: Images reflecting all the flare burning status. Output: Image classified.	Learning time Training the model shall take one day at most.
Leading indicators	Maintainability Percentage of use of the automatic work mode and reduce the money costs of burning gases.	ML problem type Classify images (computer vision technique)	Model performance The model shall be correct at least 70% of the time.	Model size The model size shall not break the inference time.	Storage The ML artifacts shall be stored in a cloud service on Microsoft Azure and recovered in an efficient way.
Customer expectations	Exploitability The system shall accurately classify the flare when burning gases.	Exploitability The model creation shall follow best coding practices (e.g., coding conventions PEP-8, SOLID design principles) and be documented according to Decoding PEP-257.			Telemetry The system shall collect summary data from user interactions so that it can be monitored.

1. In your opinion, what are the benefits of using the approach?

Your answer

2. In your opinion, what are the limitations of the approach? (e.g. completeness of ML concerns, quality of result, visualization of approach...)

Your answer

3. Regarding your perception of the ease of use, usefulness and intent of using * the approach, how much do you agree with the following statements?

Strongly disagree Partially disagree Partially agree Totally agree

I found the approach easy to use

Using the approach would be useful to support more complete and accurate specification of ML-based system requirements.

I would use the approach when I need to specify requirements for ML-based systems.

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